

Ion-Exchange Properties of Poly-(5-Acetyl-4-Hydroxy-1,3-Phenylene)-1,2-Ethanedyl with Bivalent Ions

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The polymer prepared from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and 1,2-dichloroethane by Friedel-Craft's condensation showed to be a selective chelating ion-exchange resin for copper, cobalt, manganese, zinc and iron ions. A batch equilibration method was employed in the study of the selectivity of metal ion uptake over a wide pH range and in media of various ionic strengths.

THE chelating properties of 2-hydroxyacetophenone have been intensively investigated¹⁻³. In continuation of our previous work on transition metal complexes, it was considered worthwhile to study the polymers prepared from 2-hydroxyacetophenone. Chelating ion-exchange resins prepared from copolycondensation of salicylaldehyde, 8-hydroxyquinoline or various phenol derivatives have been reported⁴⁻⁸. A chelate group suitable for use in a resin must obviously have the following properties.

(1) Be capable of resin formation or substitution in a resin matrix, (2) be sufficiently stable to withstand the polymerization or resinification reaction and (3) be compact so as not to be hindered sterically by the dense resin matrix.

The poly-(5-acetyl-4-hydroxy-1,3-phenylene)-1,2-ethanedyl abbreviated as AHPE may prove to be a more useful polymeric ligand because of the larger separation of the 2-hydroxyacetophenone units in two successive repeating units. The object of the present work is to obtain data on the ion exchange selectivity and capacity of AHPE resin. Investigation on the metal uptake and distribution ratios of metal ions at different pH have been made.

Experimental

To a well stirred and ice-cold mixture of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (7.5 ml, 0.062 mole) and 1,2-dichloroethane (10.0 ml, 0.125 mole) powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (24.9 g, 0.187 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to come to room temperature and refluxed at 100° for 3 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with ice-cold 10% aqueous hydrochloric acid. The solid product was filtered and steam distilled to remove unreacted 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 1,2-dichloroethane and dissolve in 10% alkali solution. The solid which precipitated out on acidification with 10% ice-cold hydrochloric acid, was filtered, washed

with water and dried. It was brown in colour. It was ground to pass a 150 mesh size. The sample, thus treated, was used in all the experiments described in the present communication.

Metal uptake determinations: For the determination of metal uptake by the resin in the presence of electrolytes of different concentrations for the four metals given in Table 1, the following procedure was used.

TABLE 1—EVALUATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES IN THE UPTAKE OF METAL IONS

Cation ^a	Concentration of electrolyte in <i>M</i>	Weight in mg of metal ion taken up in the presence of			
		NaNO ₃	NaCl	NaClO ₄	Na ₂ SO ₄
Cu(II)	1.0	1.08	2.16	0.57	0.25
	0.5	1.14	2.29	0.69	0.35
	0.1	1.46	2.41	0.98	0.50
	0.05	1.65	2.60	1.33	0.69
Co(II)	1.0	0.88	0.47	0.29	0.18
	0.5	1.06	0.59	0.53	0.47
	0.1	1.18	0.88	0.88	0.70
	0.05	1.29	1.18	1.35	0.88
Zn(II)	1.0	0.13	0.19	0.26	0.16
	0.5	0.39	0.39	0.42	0.26
	0.1	0.62	0.58	0.52	0.39
	0.05	0.78	0.78	0.65	0.52
Mn(II)	1.0	1.05	0.20	2.03	0.02
	0.5	0.85	0.62	1.85	0.43
	0.1	0.50	0.98	1.20	0.88
	0.05	0.25	1.22	0.90	1.26
Fe(III)	1.0	0.67	0.78	0.56	0.61
	0.5	0.78	0.89	0.78	0.84
	0.1	1.00	1.03	1.00	1.12
	0.05	1.34	1.12	1.17	1.39

^a 2 ml of M(NO₃)₂. Volume of electrolyte 40 ml, pH = 5.5 for Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Mn(II) and pH = 2.5 for Fe(III). Time: 24 hr, Temp 25°.

0.25 g of the sample was suspended in the electrolyte solution (40 ml) of known concentration. The pH of the suspension was adjusted to the required value by using either 0.1M HCl or 0.1M

NaOH. The suspension was stirred for a period of 24 hr at 25°. To this suspension 2 ml of 0.1M solution of the metal ion under study was added. The pH was adjusted to 5.5 for Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and 2.5 for Fe(III). The mixture was stirred at 25° for 24 hr and filtered. The solid was washed. The filtrate and washings were combined and estimated for the metal ion content by titration against standard edta. A blank experiment was carried out in the same manner without adding the polymer sample. The blank was also estimated for the metal ion content. The amount of metal ion taken up by the polymer in the presence of the given electrolyte of known concentration results from the difference between the blank reading and the reading in the actual experiment. The experiment was repeated in the presence of several electrolytes.

Evaluation of the rate of metal uptake : In order to estimate the time required to reach the state of equilibrium under given experimental conditions, a series of experiments of the type described above were carried out, in which the metal ion taken up by the chelating resin was estimated from time to time at 25° in presence of 40 ml of 1M NaNO₃ solution. It is assumed that under the given conditions, the state of equilibrium is established in 24 hr. The rate of metal uptake shown in Table 2 is expressed as percentage of the amount of metal ions taken up after a certain time related to that in the state of equilibrium.

Evaluation of distribution of metal ions at different pH : The distribution of each one of the five metal ions copper(II), cobalt(II), zinc(II), manganese(II) and iron(III) between polymer phase and aqueous phase was estimated at 25° and in presence of a 1M NaNO₃ solution. The experiments were carried out as described earlier at pH 1, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, 5 and 6. The distribution ratio, D, is defined by the following relation,

$$D = \frac{\text{mg of metal ions taken up by 1 g of polymer}}{\text{mg of metal ions present in 1 ml of solution}}$$

The results are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The condensation of dichloroethane with 2-hydroxyacetophenone can produce only a linear polymer because of the ortho position of 2-hydroxyphenone is occupied by the acetyl group. The inability of the polymer to grow three-dimensionally as phenol-formaldehyde polymers is possibly the main reason for the limited degree of polymerization observed. The molecular weight determined

by vapour pressure osmometry is 1050. The polymeric chelates may have the following structure :

x=2 for Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Mn(II) ; x=3 for Fe(III).

Influence of electrolytes on the metal uptake : Examination of the data presented in Table 1, reveals that the amount of Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II) ions taken up by the polymer sample increases with decreasing concentration of sodium nitrate, chloride, perchlorate or sulphate whereas the amount of Mn(II) ions taken up by the polymer increases with decreasing concentration of sodium chloride or sulphate and decreases with decreasing concentration of sodium nitrate or perchlorate. The high ionic strength of the basic electrolyte employed makes changes which occur in the overall concentration of the solution due to removal of metal ion from this solution negligible⁹.

Rate of metal uptake : Table 2, shows the dependence of the rate of metal ion uptake on the nature of the metal. Fe(III) ions require 3 hr while other metal ions take about 6 hr to attain the state of equilibrium.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE RATE OF METAL UPTAKE^a

Time in hr	Percentage of the amount of metal ion taken up ^b				
	Cu(II)	Co(II)	Zn(II)	Mn(II)	Fe(III)
0.5	12.3	10.3	8.8	23.2	33.3
1.0	25.6	24.2	15.2	34.2	55.2
2.0	35.8	36.7	31.3	42.0	75.8
3.0	50.3	48.2	52.4	56.4	99.5
4.0	68.2	69.9	72.1	63.2	
5.0	88.7	85.6	89.9	78.2	
6.0	99.4	96.8	98.2	97.8	

^aM(NO₃)₂=0.1M, volume used 2 ml.

NaNO₃=1.0M, volume used 40 ml, pH=3.

^bRelated to the amount of metal ions in the state of equilibrium (100%).

Distribution ratios of metal ions at different pH : The results of the effect of pH on the amount of metal ion distributed between two phases are presented in Table 3. Examination of the data indicates that the relative amount of metal ions taken up by the polymeric material increases with increasing pH of the medium.

The study was restricted to pH 6 in order to avoid metal hydrolysis at higher pH. With the change of pH, from 3 to 6 the distribution ratio, D, for Cu(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) increases

with a factor of 51, 3, 5 and 2 respectively while the pH change from 1 to 3 in case of Fe(III), the distribution ratio is increased by a factor of 33.

It can be seen that polymer sample is taking up Cu(II) ions more selectively than other ions under study. Thus the results of this study are helpful in selecting the optimum pH for the selective uptake of a particular metal ion from a mixture of different ions.

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION RATIO, D, OF DIFFERENT METAL IONS

pH	Distribution ratio ^a of metal ions				
	Fe(III)	Cu(II)	Co(II)	Zn(II)	Mn(II)
1.0	101				
2.0	178				
2.5	724				
3.0	3307	41	45	60	47
4.0		758	92	113	62
5.0		1029	117	229	83
6.0		2040	142	382	90

^aError ± 5%.

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